

RELAXATION PECULIARITIES OF A GAS-LIQUID MIXTURE**Mammadov A.,***Assistant professor, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University,
Baku, Azerbaijan***Sultanova A.,***Junior Research Engineer,
Scientific Research Institute**“Geotechnological Problems of Oil, Gas and Chemistry”,
Baku, Azerbaijan***Mammadov R.,***Junior Research Engineer,
Scientific Research Institute**“Geotechnological Problems of Oil, Gas and Chemistry”,
Baku, Azerbaijan***Hasanova N.***Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku, Azerbaijan***ABSTRACT**

It is known that a number of difficulties arise in the development of oil fields characterized by non-Newtonian properties. Therefore, the study of the relaxation properties of a fluid that saturates a porous medium is an important task, which in the future will effectively control the development and production of such oils. The paper proposes a technique for studying relaxation properties by the method of comprehensive compression and revealing the dependence of relaxation properties on various parameters.

Keywords: PVT bomb, saturation pressure, relaxation, system, gas-liquid mixture, heavy oil.

1. Introduction

Considering the fact that areas with oils characterized by non-Newtonian properties have recently been involved in development, the study of their properties is of particular relevance. The aim of the work is to identify the dependence of the relaxation properties of gas-liquid systems, which, in turn, will allow regulating the development and production processes and increasing their efficiency [1].

2. Methodological part

The essence of the method lies in the fact that during a fast loading or unloading of the system in the high-pressure chamber, a corresponding slow decrease or increase in pressure is observed, the dynamics of which is used to evaluate the degree of non-equilibrium of the system [1]. A slow increase or decrease in pressure is associated with structural changes, as a result of which the system is repackaged into an energetically convenient structure. Thus, the relaxation properties of macromolecular compounds are studied. Similar effects can be observed during volumetric loading of heavy oils containing resins and asphaltenes. These works show that similar phenomena occur in gas-liquid mixtures, which can be associated with the movement

of the smallest particles of dispersed gas to areas of greatest stress [2].

Below are the results obtained using this approach. The relaxation properties of gas-liquid systems at different pressure levels were studied. The proposed technique made it possible to reveal the pressure interval in the region above the saturation pressure, in which the non-equilibrium properties of gas-cut-liquids are most pronounced.

The laboratory unit for studying the relaxation properties of gas-liquid systems consists of a PVT bomb; a hydraulic press with a measuring scale; a thermostat, a manifold, exemplary pressure gauge, and a barrel for displacement fluid (see Fig. 1). The PVT bomb consists of two chambers: a high-pressure chamber, in which the test medium is placed, and a chamber with a displacement fluid (transformer oil), which is supplied by a press. Both chambers are separated from each other by a movable piston. The PVT bomb is placed in a thermostatically controlled jacket and mounted on hinges. To prepare a recombinant sample, a liquid is placed in a high-pressure chamber and a high-pressure gas is supplied. By intensive stirring, the gas is dissolved in the liquid.

Fig. 1. Experimental unit. 1-high pressure bomb, 2-thermostat, 3-press, 4-fluid reservoir, 5-manifold, 6-pressure gauges, 7-chart recorder, 8-amplifier, 9-pressure transducer

The sequence of the experiments was as follows. The studied gas-liquid mixture was prepared in the PVT bomb. The saturation pressure was determined by

the volumetric method (Fig. 2), after which the P_0 system was subjected to baro-treatment by cyclic loading to the initial pressure level much higher than the saturation pressure.

Fig. 2. Pressure versus volume curve at equilibrium conditions

3. Results and discussion

Thus, thermodynamic equilibrium was established in the system. Further, using a hydraulic press, the system was unloaded with a constant rate of pressure change at the level P_1 . After that, according to the readings of the exemplary pressure gauge, the change in pressure in the system was considered until the pressure in the system became constant. Then the next decrease in pressure was carried out by the same value ΔP with the same rate of pressure change and similar measurements were made.

The unloading of the system continued until the saturation pressure. Below are the results of studies on a recombined sample composed of transformer oil with natural gas. $P_0 = 150$ atm., $\Delta P = 10$ atm., $P_{\text{sat}} = 36$ atm. All experiments were carried out at a constant temperature $t = 40^\circ\text{C}$, which was achieved by thermostating all the main components of the installation. Figure 3 illustrates the procedure for one of the series of experiments and the observed pressure change.

Fig. 3. Difference between P_{initial} and P_{wellhead}

It has been established that at pressures much higher than the saturation pressure, no relaxation phenomena are observed with decreasing pressure. When a certain level is reached, when unloading the gas-liquid system, there is an increase in pressure, which stabilizes over a long period of time. The magnitude of the pressure increase contributes as the phase transition point is approached and is determined in each individual case

by the properties of the system itself [3-5]. For the experiments described, a change in pressure is observed starting from 40 atm. To confirm this experiment, experiments were carried out on pure transformer oil.

The system was unloaded and then loaded at a constant rate and temperature (Fig. 4). As can be seen from this graph, the unloading and loading curves of the system are identical.

Fig. 4. Unloading and Loading Curves

These results make it possible to assert that non-equilibrium effects take place only in heterogeneous systems. The noted increase in the relaxation properties makes it possible to assume that, starting from a certain characteristic value of pressure, which exceeds the saturation pressure by about 1.5–2 times, the process of nucleation, takes place. The long-term stabilization of the system pressure is explained by the processes of relaxation in disperse media, which occur when the constituent phases move. In the course of the experiment, it was revealed that the degree of non-equilibrium of the system also depends on the rate of change in pressure (and the degree of non-equilibrium was judged by the magnitude of the increase in pressure). Experiments suggest that a non-equilibrium change in pressure also contributes to the intensive formation of gas micronuclei. However, studies in the pressure range above saturation pressure made it possible to establish that at sufficiently high rates of load change, of the order of magnitude or more, the gas-liquid mixture practically does not have time to respond to external disturbances and, as a result, there is only a slight increase in pressure at the first moment of time, which is due to elastic deformation of the system. In other words, the process of nucleation is not observed.

Thus, experiments in free volume at pressures above the critical ones made it possible to establish the following: the process of formation of nuclei of a new phase in gas-liquid systems begins long before the saturation pressure when a characteristic pressure level ($\sim 1.5-2 P_{\text{sat}}$) is reached. The intensity of the nucleation process in this region depends on the rate of pressure change in the system.

Conclusions and recommendations

Studies have established that the relaxation properties of gas-cut-liquids at pressures above the critical ones are due to the processes of formation and stable existence of gaseous embryos.

From a practical point of view, the results of the experiments carried out will provide specialists with the necessary information about the relaxation properties of gas-liquid systems. At the same time, it seems possible to make a substantiated decision on the management of development and production processes, the choice of the optimal mode of operation of the "reservoir-well" system, which, in turn, will increase the efficiency of the process as a whole. It should be noted that further study of the relaxation properties of gas-liquid systems will make it possible to intensify technological processes in areas with oils with non-Newtonian properties.

References

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